

Leveraging the techniques of vigenère cipher and modern cryptographic algorithms: CryptographyApp

By

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Abstract

The growing reliance on digital communication necessitates robust methods for secure data transmission. Hence this project proposes a hybrid cryptography system integrating the Vigenère cipher with modern cryptographic techniques. The system aims to enhance security while maintaining computational efficiency. Functionalities of the system include key generation, encryption, decryption, and cryptographic analysis. The Vigenère cipher serves as the foundation for the system, providing a polyalphabetic substitution method. Additionally, modern cryptographic algorithms such as AES are integrated to strengthen security. Algorithms and methodologies employed include: Vigenère Cipher which utilizes a keyword to shift characters by different amounts, creating a polyalphabetic substitution; AES which implements symmetric-key encryption with a block cipher, ensuring confidentiality and integrity of data; Cryptographic Analysis which employs statistical analysis and frequency distribution techniques to assess the strength of the encryption and identify potential vulnerabilities. By combining classical and modern cryptographic techniques, the hybrid system aims to provide robust security while addressing the limitations of individual methods. The project contributes to the field of cryptography by exploring the synergy between historical ciphers and contemporary encryption standards.

Introduction

Cryptography plays a pivotal role in securing digital communications, ensuring confidentiality, integrity, and authenticity of data. In recent years, the surge in cyber threats necessitates the development of robust cryptographic techniques. One such approach is hybrid cryptography, which combines the strengths of multiple encryption methods of multiple encryption methods to mitigate the vulnerabilities of individual algorithms. This study focuses on the integration of the Vigenère cipher, a classical encryption technique, into modern cryptographic systems to enhance security. The Vigenère cipher, invented by Blaise de Vigenère in the 16th century, is a polyalphabetic substitution cipher characterized by its use of a keyword and multiple Caesar ciphers to encrypt plaintext. Despite its simplicity, the Vigenère cipher offers a level of security superior to mono-alphabetic ciphers due to its key variability. However, it is vulnerable to frequency analysis and Kasiski examination, limiting its effectiveness in modern cryptographic contexts. The resurgence of interest in classical cryptography techniques, coupled with advancements in computational power and cryptanalysis, has inspired researchers to explore the potential of integrating historical ciphers like the Vigenère cipher into contemporary cryptographic frameworks. By leveraging the strengths of classical and modern encryption methods, hybrid cryptographic systems can provide enhanced security against sophisticated attacks while preserving computational efficiency.

Materials and methods

1. Literature review

The first literature review was done on “File cryptography optimization based on Vigenère cipher and AES”. It was published in 2023. It was done by the authors: Muslih Kangmouise, Budi Handoko, and Aditya Rizqy. Its advantages included dual-layer enhanced security by combining the simplicity of Vigenère cipher and the robustness of AES, which helps to overcome the weaknesses of the individual algorithms. The disadvantage is that it increases computational complexity.

The second literature review was done on the “An enhanced Vigenère cipher for data security”, by Aized Amin Soofi, Irfan Riaz, Umair Rasheed. It was published in 2016 on the IJSTR. The study successfully introduced key generation method that decreases the chance of brute force attacks. The main advantage of this one is that increased key randomness provides higher security. But the disadvantage is that the added complexity can slow down encryption processes.

The third literature review was done on “CryptStego: powerful blend of cryptography for securing communications”. It was published in 2020 on Springer, by Shraiya Pandey, Pashupati Baniya, Parma Nand etc. The study successfully demonstrated secure and covert data transmission using this hybrid technique. Its main advantage is that it provides dual security by hiding the encrypted message. But the con of this is that there was increased complexity in both encoding and decoding processes.

The fourth literature review was done on “Encrypted Short Message Service Design Using Combination of Modified Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) And Vigenère Cipher Algorithm”. It was published in 2017 by the authors: Christopher, Abel Gunawan and Sheila Prima. The study revealed a hybrid system that ensures higher security for text communication over mobile networks. The advantage of this was effectiveness for securing low-bandwidth communication. However, there system requires more computational resources compared to traditional methods.

The last literature review was done on the “Vigenère Cipher: trends, Reviews and possible modifications”. It was published in 2021. It was published by the authors: Abdulrahnan Olaniyan and Al-Amin Aliyu. This review focuses on the history, usage, and modern adaptations of the Vigenère cipher, especially its integration with AES for more secure systems. The advantage is that it offers new perspectives on enhancing Vigenère for modern encryption. However, there is limited focus on practical implementation

2. Methodology

Figure 2: Agile methodology

Agile methodology, particularly Scrum, is used in the application's development. Scrum's iterative approach involves dividing the development process into "sprints" and gathering user feedback to continuously refine the application. This flexibility allows the team to adjust priorities, ensuring adaptability to changes. Agile development prioritizes collaboration, ongoing delivery, and feedback responsiveness, resulting in a more user-focused and efficient development process.

Figure 2: Scrum

3. Objectives

- Implement secure encryption and decryption
To design a robust cryptography system that incorporates the Vigenère cipher alongside contemporary encryption algorithms, AES.
- Develop a user friendly chatroom
To demonstrate the practical applicability of the cryptography approach in real-world scenarios, through the implementation of a user-friendly chatroom where users can easily send and receive messages. Users can also send private messages on the same platform to specific intended audiences.
- Provide educational cryptography FAQs
To design and implement a module that displays FAQs about cryptography, providing clear and concise answers to help users understand the principles and importance of cryptographic techniques.
- Ensure data security and integrity
To implement techniques that maintain the integrity and confidentiality of all data within the system, including message integrity and secure key management.

4. System design

Description

Designing a system involves meticulous planning to ensure it meets user needs, functions seamlessly, and meets performance standards. It involves designing the user interface and ensuring all parts work smoothly with quick response times. During development, designers use diagrams and plans to guide them, minimize errors, and provide a clear roadmap. System design considers both technical and aesthetic aspects, aiming for a user-friendly experience with a strong backend. It also includes developing prototypes, testing repeatedly, and refining the system based on user feedback. This comprehensive approach ensures the system meets user expectations and performs effectively.

System architecture

A system architecture diagram is a blueprint that illustrates the structural components and organization of an application. It depicts the physical structure, intended usage, and purpose of the application from the perspective of developers, rather than end-users. To manage complexity and promote modular development, developers subdivide the system into layers based on functionality or access pathways, such as a home page or a contact form. This layering simplifies

debugging and maintenance. System architecture also encompasses data flow between modules, defines integration points with external systems, and ensures compliance with industry standards and best practices.

Figure 4.2: System architecture

Use Case Diagram

A use case diagram outlines how users interact with a system to achieve specific goals. It shows the system's boundaries, user roles (actors), and how they interact with the system's functions. Use case diagrams help design and develop systems by capturing all possible user scenarios, ensuring that the system meets user needs. They also clarify the roles and responsibilities of different system components.

Figure 4.3: Use case diagram

Data Flow Diagram

A DFD is a visual representation of an information system's key processes and how they handle data. It outlines the system's general structure and is often used as a starting point for deeper analysis. DFDs can help in understanding data processing, identifying bottlenecks, and pinpointing areas where processes can be improved. They show the data entering the system, the steps it goes through, where it's stored, and the final output. This visual representation makes it easier to see how data is handled and processed within the system.

Figure 4.4: DFD

5. System development

Module description

The module description offers a detailed analysis of a particular module in a software system or app. It's a comprehensive guide that explains the module's purpose, what it does, and its role in the system's overall design. By providing a clear understanding of each module, the module description helps developers understand the system as a whole, work together effectively, and maintain it over time. Each module has its own set of tasks and interacts with other modules in a way that keeps the system running smoothly and as a whole.

- **Message encryption**

This module involves converting the plain text of the first user into cipher text. The user enters the data and a predefined key for the Vigenère cipher to turn it into cipher text. For the AES encryption, the user uses their own secret key to encrypt the message, which can also be used for decryption. This module ensures that sensitive information is securely encrypted, making it inaccessible to unauthorized users. The encryption process must be efficient and robust, providing strong security without significantly impacting system performance.

- **Message decryption**

This module involves converting encrypted/cipher text back into plain text. The second user enters the cipher text and the predefined key for Vigenère or the user's key for AES to decrypt the ciphered text. The decryption process must be reliable and user-friendly, allowing authorized users to easily retrieve the original message while maintaining the confidentiality and integrity of the data.

- **Chat section**

This is a section that allows users on the system to send and receive messages to and from other users. It has been implemented in such a way that users can send public and private messages to each other. The private messages are accessed using the “/private + username” technique that enable users to send messages to other users of their choice on a platform harboring many users. These private messages are only seen by the sender and intended receivers. Otherwise, the public messages are for all users connected to the server.

- **FAQs section**

This is a module which displays the frequently asked questions about cryptography in general and not specific to this system. It is very essential as it provides more and descriptive information about cryptography that can be easily understood by users new to the concept.

- **Image steganography**

Image steganography is a type of encryption where messages can be hidden in images using various techniques like the traditional LSB. Similar in this module, users are able to encrypt or embed secret messages in images. This module makes use of the spread spectrum technique. This is a technique in steganography where bits of the message are spread or scattered across the image without changing its appearance or shape. The images are then shared among users to transmit these secret messages. The receiver inputs the image with the message in order to extract it and display it on the message box.

- **Video steganography**

Video steganography is a type of encryption where messages can be hidden in videos using various techniques like the traditional LSB. Similar in this module, users are able to encrypt or embed secret messages in videos or video files. This module makes use of the spread spectrum technique. This is a technique in steganography where bits of the message are spread or scattered across the video without changing its appearance or shape. The video or videos are then shared among users to transmit these secret messages. The receiver inputs the video which has been embedded with the message in order to extract the message and display it on the message box.

- **Encrypted Chat section**

This module provides maximum security to the chat section as another type of encryption happens. Here, the messages are encrypted again on the sender's side and only displays and transmits cipher text. The receiver however, received decrypted text and the plain text is displayed on the receiver's end.

6. Algorithm

An algorithm is a well-defined set of instructions or step-by-step- procedure used to solve a specific problem or accomplish a particular task. It is a computational procedure that takes an input, performs a series of operational or computations, and produces an output. Algorithm can be found in various fields. They provide a systematic approach to problem-solving and crucial in designing efficient and effective solutions. The system uses the following algorithms:

- **Vigenère**

The Vigenère cipher is an algorithm for encrypting alphabetic text by using a simple form of polyalphabetic substitution. Instead of shifting all letters by the same amount, it uses a keyword to determine different shift amounts for each letter in the message. This makes it more complex and harder to crack than simple Caesar ciphers. The Vigenère cipher provides a higher level of security compared to mono-alphabetic ciphers and is often used for its simplicity and effectiveness in encrypting text data.

- **Advanced Encryption standard algorithm**

AES is a widely used encryption algorithm designed to secure sensitive data. It operates by transforming blocks of data, typically 128 bits at a time, using a series of substitution, permutation, and mixing operations. AES employs a symmetric key system, meaning the same key is used for both encryption and decryption. Its efficiency, security, and widespread adoption make it suitable for various applications, including securing communication channels, protecting data, and ensuring the confidentiality and integrity of information. AES is known for its robustness and resistance to attacks, making it a preferred choice for encryption in modern cryptographic systems.

Results and Discussions

The system provides encrypted cipher text of the plain text to the user. The system provides decrypted plain text of the cipher text to the user. Users are able to send and receive each other messages on the chat room. Also users can send private messages to each other on the chat section without others seeing, using the /private feature. The system does display the FAQs and their corresponding answers. The system does correctly and smoothly embed and extract messages to and from images using the spread spectrum technique. The system does correctly and smoothly embed and extract messages to and from videos using the spread spectrum technique. The chat section encrypts the message before sending and only displays the encrypted message on the sender's end and displays decrypted text on the receiver's end.

In conclusion, the project has achieved its objectives, delivering a functional application for encrypting text using Vigenère cipher with a twist of modern cryptographic algorithms, AES. The project has been successfully completed with all deliverables meeting the requirements. This project's documentation has presented a comprehensive overview of the application. The objective of the project was to design and develop an application that will help people encrypt and send messages through a secure communication channel. Throughout the documentation, we have discussed various aspects of the project, including system analysis, specifications, design, implementation, and future enhancements. The project has been of great help for me in gaining valuable information on software development. It has given me a great satisfaction in having designed an application that has importance in the real world. The project's success opens doors for future improvements, advancements, and potential collaborations to further enhance the application's capabilities and reach a wider audience in need of secure and proper transfer encrypted messages.

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